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Evidence for rapid NLR-cargo/substrate interactions.

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Citations

1. Zhu, Q., Wong, A.K., Krishnan, A., Aure, M.R., Tadych, A., Zhang, R., Corney, D.C., Greene, C.S., Bongo, L.A., Kristensen, V.N. and Charikar, M., 2015. Targeted exploration and analysis of large cross-platform human transcriptomic compendia. *Nature methods*, 12(3), pp.211-214.